

INFLUENCE OF INTERPHASE MATERIAL PROPERTY GRADIENTS ON THE MICROMECHANICS OF FIBROUS THERMOSETTING-MATRIX COMPOSITES

F. Yang and R. Pitchumani*
Composites Processing Laboratory
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Connecticut
Storrs, Connecticut 06269-3139
*Corresponding Author

ABSTRACT: Both experimental and theoretical studies in the literature have shown that a fiber surface perturbs its surrounding polymer to create a three-dimensional interphase zone with concentration gradients. The interphase region serves as a buffer between the bulk matrix and fiber, and its properties are critical to the overall composite performance. The concentration gradients in the interphase reflect different local stoichiometric ratios, which may be correlated to material properties (e.g., the modulus) via experimental studies. Micromechanical stress analysis needs the interphase material properties as input information. Since relatively scant information is available on the prediction of interphase concentration gradients as function of processing conditions, the material property profiles in an interphase are not readily determined. Consequently, current micromechanical analyses have resorted to using assumed interphase property profiles. An analysis using the property variation corresponding to an actual interphase composition profile is imperative for a realistic property and performance prediction, and forms the focus of the study. Such an analysis also provides for potentially relating the processing parameters to the composite properties, and in turn, for optimal processing of composites.

KEYWORDS: Interphase formation, Micromechanics, Finite element method, Elastic moduli

INTRODUCTION

Fabrication of thermosetting-matrix composites is based on a critical step of cure, which involves applying predefined temperature cycle to a fiber-resin matrix mixture. The elevated temperatures initiate a crosslinking cure reaction among the species in the matrix. The presence of fibers has been found to significantly influence the cure reaction, resulting in the formation of a third phase known as the interphase which possesses property gradient distinct from those of the bulk fiber and the matrix. The interphase resides in a region between the original constituents of the composite with a size of a few to a few thousand nanometers [1-4]. Although the region has a microscopic scale, it essentially forms a significant portion of the matrix in the composite [1]. Also, the performance of the composite is determined by the ability of the matrix to transfer load to the reinforcing fiber, and is thus controlled by the interphase region. The structure and properties of the interphase are the dominant factors governing the overall composite properties and performance.

Several physical and chemical mechanisms contribute simultaneously to the interphase formation and very few of them have been described rigorously in mathematical models. Garton *et al.* [5] showed that the carbon surfaces influence the cross-linking reaction in an anhydride-epoxy system by adsorbing the tertiary amine catalyst and forming amine rich interphase regions near the carbon surfaces. Similarly, Sellitti *et al.* [6] used Fourier transform IR attenuated total reflection spectroscopy to characterize the interphase phenomena in an epoxy-anhydride-catalyst system, and showed that the surface species

introduced on graphitized carbon fibers can promote or inhibit the cross-linking process by the preferential adsorption of the catalyst. Other possible interphase mechanisms are proposed by Drzal [4].

The effects of interphase property gradients on the overall composite properties are extensively investigated in the literature [7–15, for example]. However, the studies are commonly based on assumed or empirical interphase property profiles. Tsai *et al.* used an axisymmetric finite element model to study the interface stress, displacement, and fracture toughness [7]. An elastic shear lag analysis was developed and correlated with the micro-debonding test data to determine the thickness and material properties of the interphase. Boundary element method was adopted by Liu *et al.* to predict transverse moduli of fibrous composites [8]. Tsui *et al.* studied the effects of different interphase properties on Young's modulus, maximum stress concentration factor, and stress distribution in particle-filled polymer composites [9]. Transverse Young's storage/loss moduli and physical aging of a viscoelastic composite with fiber reinforcement were investigated by Fisher and Brinson [10]. All the studies in refs. [8-10] assumed an interphase thickness and modulus.

Some empirical relations were proposed to predict the interphase property gradients. By assuming that the rate of change of a property is proportional to the value of the property, the interphase modulus variation with radius, $E_i(r)$, was given as [11,12]:

$$E_i(r) = E_m \left[1 + \left(pE_f / E_m - 1 \right) \frac{1 - re^{1-r/r_i} / r_i}{1 - r_f e^{1-r_f/r_i} / r} \right] \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts i , m , and f refer to interphase, matrix, and fiber, respectively. The parameter p is called an adhesion factor, which is the ratio between the interphase modulus at $r=r_f$ and the fiber modulus.

$$p = E_i(r_f) / E_f$$

Similar expressions were applied to other elastic moduli and the Poisson's ratios. Thermal stresses due to the interphase property gradients are predicted by Sottos, *et al.*, where the elastic constants vary *linearly* within the interphase [13]. A power law relation was used by Wacker *et al.* to calculate transverse Young's modulus of composites [14].

$$E_i(r) = (\alpha E_f - E_m) \left[\frac{r_i - r}{r_i - r_f} \right]^n + E_m \quad (2)$$

where $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$, and $n = 2, 3, \dots$. A review on the empirical interphase models and their features was given by Jayaraman *et al.* [15].

Due to complexities of the molecular level mechanisms that occur in the vicinity of the fibers during the process, prediction of the interphase evolution as function of processing parameters from first principles has been the subject of little attention. To the authors' knowledge, the first work on modeling interphase formation in thermosetting materials was presented by Palmese [1]. The model predicted the interphase composition profile under thermodynamic equilibrium conditions of a non-reacting epoxy-amine resin system. Minimum free energy principle was invoked to set up the equilibrium state, accounting enthalpy interaction between fiber surface and resin components, and the calculation of Gibbs free energy was based on a Flory-Huggins type lattice structure. Hrivnak extended Palmese's model to a reacting system by using renewal theory models to the construction of the assembly Gibbs free energy and the associated

Figure 1 Unit cell considered in the analysis

chemical potential [16]. In an alternative approach, a kinetics-based description of the governing phenomena was developed by the authors to predict the interphase development during thermosetting composite processing [17,18]. In this method, mass conservation principle was employed to describe the transport processes of multilayer adsorption, desorption and diffusion near a fiber surface, which are accompanied by simultaneous cure reaction between the resin components. The time evolution of interphase concentration profile gradients before the gelation of the thermosetting system was predicted as function of material and process parameters.

The goal of this work is to use an existing interphase concentration evolution model to predict the interphase composition profiles, which are subsequently mapped to modulus profiles using an experimental correlation between compositions and moduli. To this end, the model of Hrivnak [16] is used for the interphase composition prediction, while the kinetics-based description will be reported in a future work. The modulus profiles mapped from the interphase concentration gradients are used in finite element analyses to calculate the stiffness of fiber reinforced epoxy/amine composites. A commonly used representative volume element (RVE), i.e., the rectangular unit cell in the right-hand-side schematic in Fig. 1, is adopted in the numerical studies. The effects of several processing parameters on the overall composite modulus are illustrated.

INTERPHASE FORMATION MODEL

To eliminate the need for assumed interphase properties in current micromechanical analyses, the interphase formation model by Hrivnak is adopted to describe the concentration profiles in the interphase region [16]. The model examines the chain/surface and chain/chain interactions of a binary thermosetting resin mixture in the vicinity of a fiber surface. The interaction of a single polymer chain with a surface is described by an analytical molecular partition function, which is incorporated into a sub-lattice model to derive the chain assembly Gibbs free energy. By minimizing the assembly Gibbs free energy, the volume fraction of species I at the (z) th lattice layer, $v_I(z)$, is obtained as follows.

$$v_1(z) = \kappa v_1(\infty) \underbrace{q(x_1, z) \exp[S_1(z)]}_{\text{Chain/Surface Interaction}} \underbrace{\exp[\chi(v_2^2(\infty) - v_2^2(z))]}_{\text{Chain/Chain Interaction}} \underbrace{\exp\left[\frac{[v_1(z) - v_1(\infty)]}{N_L} (1 - x_1/x_2)\right]}_{\text{Excess Mixing}} \quad (3)$$

where

$$q(x_1, z) = 1 - \sqrt{2/\pi x_1} (1 - e^{\omega_1/kT}) \operatorname{erfc}(z/\sigma_1) \quad (4)$$

$$S_1(z) = \frac{\omega_1}{kT} \exp\left(\frac{\omega_1}{kT}\right) \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi x_1}} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{z}{\sigma_1}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_1^2 = c \frac{x_1 l^2}{3} \quad (6)$$

Similar expressions for species 2 may be obtained by switching the subscripts 1 and 2 in the above equations. The parameter κ is introduced as a normalization constant to ensure that volume fractions $v_1(z)$ and $v_2(z)$ sum to unity, and $v_1(\infty)$ is the volume fraction of species 1 in the far region. Eqs. (4) and (5) show that chain/surface interaction depends on the *surface potential*, ω_1 , chain length, x_1 , number of the lattice layers from the surface, z , and the temperature, T . Positive, negative, and zero values of ω_1 correspond to attractive, repulsive, and neutral surfaces to the species 1, respectively. The second exponential term in Eq. (3) accounts for the chain/chain interaction between the two species in the binary resin mixture, where χ is the *interaction parameter*. For $\chi > 0$, the two species are repulsive to each other. If the surface prefers to adsorb species 1, positive chain/chain interaction pushes the species 2 further away from the surface, leading to enhanced preferential adsorption on species 1. The last exponential term in Eq. (3) represents the effect of *excess mixing* causing by different chain lengths (x_1 and x_2) of the species. The quantity N_L is the number of lattice layers of thickness l^0 contained within a sub-lattice, and may be treated as a weighting factor of the *excess mixing*. Note that large values of N_L reduce the effect of *excess mixing*.

Fig. 2 presents a few sample concentration profiles predicted by the above model. The thermosetting mixture consists of an aliphatic bis(p-aminocyclohexyl) methane (PACM20) curing agent and an aromatic diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) epoxy resin. In the following discussion, the subscripts 1 and 2 are converted to A and E to denote the resin components PACM20 and DGEBA, respectively. Note that the volume fraction of PACM20 is converted to a parts per hundred (i.e., *pph*) concentration, defined as the weight percentage of PACM20 to DGEBA.

$$pph = 100 \frac{\rho_A v_A}{\rho_E (1 - v_A)} \quad (7)$$

where v_A is the volume fraction of PACM20, and ρ_A and ρ_E are density of PACM20 and DGEBA, respectively. Fig. 2(a) shows the distribution of pph PACM20 from the fiber surface (Layer 0) to the far region (Layer 100) at different surface potentials ω_A . The results correspond to the parameter combination of $\omega_E = -0.28 kT$, $x_E = x_A = 150$, $\chi = 1.0$, $N_L = 2.5$, as determined by Hrivnak for the DGEBA/PACM20 system [16]. For a neutral surface, the pph PACM20 values near the fiber surface are close to the bulk value of 28. The surface concentrations increase as the surface becomes more attractive to PACM20, and sharp increases are observed for $\omega_A > 1.6 kT$. As the distance increases, the pph PACM20 decreases asymptotically to the bulk value (28) for all the values of ω_A . Fig. 2(b) presents the effect of chain lengths, following the presentation format of Fig. 2(a), for the parameter combination of $\omega_A = 0.43 kT$; all other parameters retain the value as in Fig. 2(a). Fig. 2(b) shows that the surface may easily adsorb shorter chains, and the pph concentration at the surface is almost doubled as compared to the bulk value for the case of $x_E = x_A = 10$. However, the magnitudes of the surface concentration increases are not as significant as those in Fig. 2(a). It is also observed that the region perturbed by the surface becomes smaller as the chain length decreases. The discussion on the interphase formation model here only provides the

Figure 2 Interphase concentration profile predicted using the model by Hrivnak [16] for different (a) surface potentials, and (b) chain lengths.

necessary information for the development of the micromechanical analysis in this paper; the reader is referred to Hrivnak for further details [16].

INTERPHASE MODULUS PROFILES

Since matrix modulus is determined by the resin component compositions, the concentration profiles in Fig. 2 may be mapped to modulus profiles. Fig. 3 presents several experimental data on matrix modulus as function of the parameter $X = pph-1/pph$ for the DGEBA/PACM20 system at 30°C [19]. Two peaks of maximal modulus are observed: one around 18 pph PACM20 with a value of 3.2 GPa, and the other between 48 and 56 pph PACM20 having a value of 2.4 GPa. For concentrations between 18 pph and 56 pph, the value of modulus varies about 60%. The modulus drops sharply on both ends of the concentration axis due to the fact that the matrix is in extreme deficit of either resin component and can not be cured sufficiently. Based on these observations, a twin peak function is developed in this study to fit the data as follows:

$$E = \left[\frac{(X - 19.57)^2}{214.42} + 0.42 \right]^{-1} + \left[\frac{(X - 50.59)^2}{803.09} + 0.47 \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

Figure 3 The Young's modulus as a function of stoichiometry for the system DGEBA/PACM20 at 30°C.

Eq. (8) has the asymptotic value of 0 as pph approaches 0 and infinity, and it is used in this study to map the concentration profiles, $v_A(z)$ or $v_E(z)$, to modulus profile, $E(r)$. Note that the radius distance from a fiber center, r , may be obtained from the fiber radius, r_f , and the lattice layer, z , as $r = r_f + z l^0$.

The interphase region is typically thin, consequently, most micromechanical models consider only a single uniform interphase layer with thickness δ_i and effective modulus E_i [7-15]. An "interphase thickness" may be defined in a similar way as the boundary layer thickness in fluid mechanics, such as the PACM20 concentration is within 1% of the PACM20 concentration in the far region layers [17,18]. The

modulus profile, $E(r)$, may be used to determine the effective interphase modulus as follows [14].

$$E_i = (r_i - r_f) / \int_{r_f}^{r_i} \frac{dr}{E(r)} \quad (9)$$

The derivation of Eq. (9) is based on a series connection of an infinite number of springs.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF LAMINAE TRANSVERSE MODULI

The moduli of an apparent heterogeneous composite lamina (represented by a RVE) are defined as those of an ideal equivalent macroscopic homogeneous medium. The equivalent material is generally anisotropic, and exhibits the same volume and deformation strain energy as the RVE [14,20].

$$V^{eq} = V; \quad U^{eq} = U \quad (10)$$

where V and U are the volume and strain energy of the RVE, and V^{eq} and U^{eq} are the same quantities for the equivalent material, respectively.

The RVE considered in the present study is shown in Fig. 1, where the cross-sections in the x-y plane are rectangular with length a and height b . To calculate composite moduli, appropriate boundary conditions are essential to model different loading situations [20]. The following boundary conditions are considered for determination of transverse Young's moduli [14,20].

$$\begin{aligned} u(0, y) = 0; \quad u(a, y) = \text{constant} = \delta_2 \\ v(x, 0) = 0; \quad v(x, b) = \text{constant} = \delta_3 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where u and v denote displacement in the x and y directions, respectively.

The strain energy of the *equivalent material* subject to the loading conditions in Eq. (11) is as follows

$$U^{eq} = 0.5 \int_V C_{ij} \Phi_i \Phi_j dV = 0.5 C_{ij} \Phi_i \Phi_j V$$

where C_{ij} are the components of stiffness matrix of the *equivalent material*, and Φ_i and Φ_j are macrostrains in the contracted notations. Note that the macrostrains are constants within the homogeneous *equivalent material*. Similarly, the strain energy of the RVE may be written as:

$$U = 0.5 \int_V c_{ij} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j dV$$

where the stiffnesses, c_{ij} , and the microstrains ε_i and ε_j are functions of locations in the RVE. The RVE strain energy U is computed using ABAQUS V6.3, a commercial finite element package. Substituting the above two expressions into Eq. (10) yields

$$0.5 C_{ij} \Phi_i \Phi_j V = 0.5 \int_V c_{ij} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j dV \quad (12)$$

By introducing sufficient number of admissible deformation states of the RVE, Eq. (12) may be used repetitively to form a set of linear algebraic equations which, in turn, can be used to determine all the stiffness components of the *equivalent* (or composite) material.

Three deformation states are configured by specifying the following requirements for the boundary conditions in Eq. (11).

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{state I: } & \delta_2 \neq 0, \delta_3 = 0 \\
\text{state II: } & \delta_2 \neq 0, \delta_3 \neq 0 \\
\text{state III: } & \delta_2 = 0, \delta_3 \neq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where the subscripts 2 and 3 correspond to the directions x and y , respectively, as shown in Fig. 1. The macrostrains in the *equivalent material* corresponding to the deformation states are

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{state I: } & \Phi_2^I = \delta_2 / a, \Phi_3^I = 0, \Phi_{23}^I = 0 \\
\text{state II: } & \Phi_2^{II} = \delta_2 / a, \Phi_3^{II} = \delta_3 / b, \Phi_{23}^{II} = 0 \\
\text{state III: } & \Phi_2^{III} = 0, \Phi_3^{III} = \delta_3 / b, \Phi_{23}^{III} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Combining Eqs. (12) and (14) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{state I: } & 0.5C_{22}(\Phi_2^I)^2 V = U_I \\
\text{state II: } & 0.5 \left[C_{22}(\Phi_2^{II})^2 + C_{23}\Phi_2^{II}\Phi_3^{II} + C_{33}(\Phi_3^{II})^2 \right] V = U_{II} \\
\text{state III: } & 0.5C_{33}(\Phi_3^{III})^2 V = U_{III}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where U_I, U_{II}, U_{III} are the strain energies of the RVE (obtained from FEM analysis) for deformation states *I, II* and *III* respectively. Eq. (15) may be used to solve the stiffnesses C_{22}, C_{23} , and C_{33} , which, in turn, are used to determine transverse longitudinal moduli of composite laminae.

In this study, a lamina is considered to be an orthotropic material, and has two independent transverse longitudinal moduli, E_2 and E_3 (Fig. 1). Under plain stress conditions, the relationships between the stiffnesses and the elastic constants are [21,22]:

$$C_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{23}^2 E_3 / E_2}; \quad C_{23} = \frac{\nu_{23} E_3}{1 - \nu_{23}^2 E_3 / E_2}; \quad C_{33} = \frac{E_3}{1 - \nu_{23}^2 E_3 / E_2} \tag{16}$$

where ν_{23} is Poisson's ratio. The solutions of the elastic constants in Eq. (16) are

$$E_2 = C_{22} \left[1 - \frac{C_{23}^2}{C_{22}C_{33}} \right]; \quad E_3 = C_{33} \left[1 - \frac{C_{23}^2}{C_{22}C_{33}} \right]; \quad \nu_{23} = C_{23} / C_{33} \tag{17}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The finite element analysis of the composite elastic moduli, based on Eqs. (15) and (17), were conducted for a wide range of parameters. However, only a few sample results are presented here in the interest of brevity. Prior to presentation of the results, the model was validated through comparison with calculations of Wacker *et al.* [14] at different interphase moduli, as shown in Table 1. It must be pointed out that the

assumption of transverse isotropy is used in ref. (14), which is a special case of the orthotropic medium considered in this study. By setting the array angle γ to 45° (Fig. 1), the orthotropic solutions are reduced to the corresponding transverse isotropic solutions ($E_2 = E_3$). The RVE used in the comparison study is a rectangular array ($\gamma = 45^\circ$) with 50% fiber volume fraction. The properties and the geometries of the constituent materials, Epoxy/E-glass, are:

$$E_f = 84\text{GPa}; \nu_f = 0.22; r_f = 8.5\mu\text{m}$$

$$E_m = 4\text{GPa}; \nu_m = \nu_i = 0.34; r_i = 9.5\mu\text{m}$$

where ν denotes the Poisson's ratio. Current finite element analysis uses eight-noded quadratic plane stress elements, and mesh convergence studies were conducted to determine the appropriate discretization to ensure converged modulus values. Good agreement between the FEM predictions and the literature results is observed for all the values of the interphase modulus studied, as noted in Table 1.

Table 1 Interphase effect on the transverse elastic modulus of an epoxy/E-glass composite lamina

E_i GPa	Present FEM	Wacker <i>et al.</i> [14]
4	12.15	12.25
6	13.70	13.71
8	14.66	14.68
12	15.79	15.91

With the validated FEM formulation as basis, effects of the processing parameters on the composite modulus are described in the following discussion. An examination of the interphase formation model shows that the following processing parameters are of primary interests: (1) surface potentials for chain/surface interaction, ω_A and ω_E , (2) interaction parameter for chain/chain interaction, χ , (3) lattice layer thickness, l^o , (4) number of lattice layer within a sub-lattice, N_L , and (5) chain lengths, x_E and x_A . The DGEBA/PACM20 thermosetting system is considered in the parametric studies, however, all the analyses are readily extended to a general two-component thermosetting system. At the stoichiometric point (28 pph PACM20), the modulus of the DGEBA/PACM20 system, E_m , has a value of 2.3 GPa. The interphase modulus profiles are obtained by combining Eqs. (3) and (8), and effective interphase modulus, E_i , is calculated from Eq. (9). Relevant numerical results are presented for the first time where composite stiffness is directly linked to the processing parameters without assumed structures or properties of the interphase. The results are aimed at providing guidelines for selecting material components and processing temperatures to achieve desired overall composite properties.

Fig. 4(a) shows the dimensionless composite transverse Young's modulus, E_2/E_m , as a function of fiber modulus ratio, E_f/E_m at different surface potentials ω_A . The results correspond to a parameter combination of $\nu_f = 0.5$, $\gamma = 45^\circ$; all other parameters retain the value as in Fig. 2(a). For the case of $\omega_A = 0$, the fiber surface is neutral to PACM20, and its concentration near the surface is almost identical to that of the far region [see Fig. 2(a)]. Consequently, the composite material is similar to a two components (fiber and matrix) system without distinct interphase regions. When $E_f/E_m = 1$, the curve starts at $E_2/E_m = 1$ since the material is essentially homogeneous. The composite modulus is seen to increase with increasing fiber modulus, as physically expected. However, the increase rate of E_2 slows down at larger E_f values; as $E_f \rightarrow \infty$, E_2 approaches an asymptotic value, which is obtained from an ideal rigid body reinforcement.

Interphases richer in PACM20 are developed as ω_A increases. When ω_A increases from 0 to 1.6 kT, the pph PACM20 at the fiber surface increases from 28 to 115, while the interphase modulus E_i decreases 38 percent from 2.30 GPa to 1.43 GPa. Since the interphase thickness is thin (about 0.12 microns), the composite modulus exhibits only a slight decrease corresponding to this effect. Further increases of

Figure 4 Transverse Young's modulus of composite as a function of the ratio E_f/E_m for different (a) surface potentials, and (b) chain/chain interactions.

surface potential to 1.8 kT and 2.0 kT yield sharp decreases of E_i to 0.67 GPa and 0.24 GPa, respectively, and significant decreases of the E_2 are observed. At $\omega_A = 3.5$ kT, the interphase almost consists of pure PACM20, which corresponds to a near zero value of E_i . In this case, the composite modulus is close to that of a matrix with holes, and the influence of the fiber is negligible. In Fig. 4(b), the influence of the chain/chain interaction, χ , on the composite modulus is demonstrated. The result corresponds to $\omega_A = 0.43$ kT, with all the other parameters retaining their values as in Fig. 4(a). Recall that positive chain/chain interaction enhances the preferential adsorption on PACM20; therefore, the influence of χ is similar to that of surface potential ω_A . Discussion of the trends in Fig. 4(b) follows those in Fig. 4(a), and is omitted here for brevity.

The influence of other parameters on the overall composite properties can be discussed in similar ways as will be presented in a future publication [23]. In this paper, the interphase formation is predicted by a thermodynamic approach, where the temperature is taken as a given constant. For nonisothermal cure processes, the real temperature field needs to be solved by considering the energy equation written for the whole composite domain, and the kinetics model [17,18] is to be coupled with the energy equation to predict the interphase evolution and the final composite properties. Overall, the paper introduces a systematic methodology for establishing processing-interphase-property relationships for thermosetting composite materials.

CONCLUSIONS

An interphase formation model obtained from first principles is adopted to predict the stiffness of a fibrous composite, eliminating the need for assumed interphase properties. Processing parameters such as the surface potentials and chain/chain interaction are directly linked for the first time to the overall composite properties. Parametric studies on DGEBA/PACM20 thermosetting composites reveal that transverse stiffness of the composites strongly depends on the chain/surface and chain/chain interactions. The transverse Young's modulus shows a monotonic decrease as surface potential ω_A or interaction parameter χ increase, due to softer interphases with higher PACM20 concentration.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work reported in this paper was funded in part by the National Science Foundation (Grant No. CTS-9912093) and the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (Grant No. F496200110521). We are grateful to

Prof. P. Zhang and Mr. W. Xie of University of Connecticut for their suggestions on finite element modeling.

REFERENCES

1. Palmese GR. Origin and influence of interphase material property gradients in thermosetting composites. University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials, Technical Report Number 92-25, 1992.
2. Subramanian S, Lesko JJ, Reifsnider KL, Stinchcomb WW. Characterization of the fiber-matrix interphase and its influence on mechanical properties of unidirectional composites. *Journal of Composites Materials* 1996;30:309--32.
3. Rydin RW, Varelidis PC, Papaspyrides CD, Karbhari VM. Glass fabric vinyl-ester Composites: tailoring the fiber bundle/matrix interphase with nylon coating to modify energy absorption behavior. *Journal of Composite Materials* 1997;31:182--209.
4. Drzal LT. The interphase in epoxy composites. *Advances in Polymer Sciences* 1986;75:1--32.
5. Garton A, Stevenson WTK, Wang S. Interfacial reactions in carbon-epoxy composites. *British Polymer Journal* 1987;19:459--67.
6. Sellitti C, Koenig JL, Ishida H. Surface characterization of carbon fibers and interphase phenomena in epoxy-reinforced composites. *Materials Science and Engineering* 1990;A126:235--44.
7. Tsai HC, Arocho AM, Gause LW. Prediction of fiber-matrix interphase properties and their influence on interface stress, displacement and fracture toughness of composite material. *Materials Science and Engineering* 1990;A126:295--304.
8. Liu YJ, Xu N, Luo JF. Modeling of interphases in fiber-reinforced composites under transverse loading using the boundary element method. *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 2000;67:41--9.
9. Tsui CP, Tang CY, Lee TC. Finite element analysis of polymer composites filled by interphase coated particles. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* 2001;117:105--10.
10. Fisher FT, Brinson LC. Viscoelastic interphases in polymer-matrix composites: theoretical models and finite-element analysis. *Composites Science and Technology* 2001;61:731--48.
11. Papanicolaou GC, Michalopoulou MV, Anifantis NK. Thermal stresses in fibrous composites incorporating hybrid interphase regions. *Composites Science and Technology* 2002;62:1881--194.
12. Anifantis NK. Micromechanical stress analysis of closely packed fibrous composites. *Composites Science and Technology* 2000;60:1241--48.
13. Sottos NR, McCullough RL, Guceri SI. Thermal Stresses due to property gradients at the fiber/matrix interface. in Mechanics of Composites Materials and Structures, Reddy JN, Tepy JL eds., *American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, 1989;11--20.
14. Wacker G, Bledzki AK, Chate A. Effect of interphase on the transverse Young's modulus of glass/epoxy composites. *Composites Part A* 1998;29A:619--26.
15. Jayaraman K, Reifsnider KL, Swain RE. Elastic and thermal effects in the interphase: part II. Comments on modeling studies. *Journal of Composites Technology & Research* 1993;15:14--22.
16. Hrivnak J. Interphase formation in reacting systems. University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials, Technical Report Number 97-05, 1997.
17. Yang F, Pitchumani R. A kinetics model for interphase formation in thermosetting-matrix composites. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* in press.
18. Yang F. Investigations on interface and interphase development in polymer-matrix composite materials. Ph. D. Dissertation, University of Connecticut, Department of Mechanical Engineering, 2002.
19. VanLandingham MR, Eduljee RF, Gillespie JW Jr. Relationships between stoichiometry, microstructure, and properties for amine-cured epoxies. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 1999;71:699--712.
20. Sun CT, Vaidya RS. Prediction of composite properties from a representative volume element. *Composites Science and Technology* 1996;56:171--9.
21. Yu YY. Vibrations of elastic plates: linear and nonlinear dynamical modeling of sandwiches, laminated composites, and piezoelectric layers. Springer-Verlag New York, Inc. 1996.
22. Jones RM. Mechanics of composite materials. Taylor & Francis, Inc. 1999.
23. Yang F., Pitchumani R. Micromechanical analysis of fibrous composites in relation to interphase composition profiles, *Composites Science and Technology*, Submitted, 2003.